

Al-Rich Cu/CuO_x Catalyst in a CO₂-Reduction Tandem Electrolyzer with CO-Enriched Gas Feed for Enhanced C₂₊-Products Selectivity

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Electrochemical CO₂ conversion is an important strategy to produce high-value carbon-containing molecules, such as ethylene and ethanol. Despite huge progress in recent years concerning CO₂ reduction catalyst development with increased selectivity, high selectivity for C₂₊ products at high current densities is still a challenge. We report the development and optimization of a new surface Al-rich Cu/CuO_x catalyst with high selectivity for C₂₊-products at high current densities of up to -800 mA cm^{-2} . We integrated the corresponding catalyst-modified gas-diffusion electrode into a second flow-through

electrolyzer, which was connected to a first flow-through electrolyzer comprising a highly CO-selective Ni-Cu dual-atom N-doped carbon catalyst. The enrichment of the CO₂ stream with CO generated at a current density of -400 mA cm^{-2} in the first electrolyzer increased the production rate of ethanol formation at the Al-rich Cu/CuO_x catalyst at a current density of -300 mA cm^{-2} by 28%, while maintaining the production rate of ethylene. Thereby, the overall yield of C₂₊-products obtained by CO₂ reduction was significantly increased.

Introduction

The electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) is a promising method to decrease CO₂ emissions and produce valuable products at the same time. Multi-carbon products (C₂₊) such as ethylene and ethanol are of particular economic interest, with an estimated market size of 230 and 75 billion US \$, respectively.^[1] However, the CO₂RR suffers from low selectivity for the production of C₂₊-products, especially at high current densities, which would require costly post-separation of the obtained product mixture. Steering the selectivity from other by-products, such as carbon monoxide (CO) or formic acid, towards C₂₊-products is challenging, and only a design of suitable catalyst surfaces can enhance the C₂₊ pathway over

CO, formate, or methane formation.^[2] It is widely accepted that after initial CO₂ activation, an adsorbed CO* intermediate is formed, which undergoes a C–C coupling step to form adsorbed *OC–CO species. Subsequent hydrogenation of H₂CCHO* leads either to ethylene by a dehydroxylation pathway or additional hydrogenation (H₃CCH₂O*) occurs to enter the ethanol pathway.^[3] Therefore, choosing a catalyst with optimized adsorption energies for CO₂, water, and the involved reaction intermediates is essential in CO₂RR.^[4] Copper is known to be the only single metal catalyst to adsorb *CO and H* moderately enough to produce multi-carbon products.^[5–7] The energy barrier of C–C coupling is substantially reduced using catalysts with Cu(I) species resulting in an accelerated rate of C₂₊-product formation.^[7,8] However, the selectivity of such systems towards C₂₊-products decreases when Cu(I) is reduced to Cu(0) at higher cathodic potentials, which may be required to attain relevant current densities.^[9]

To further enhance the selectivity towards multi-carbon products, tandem systems can be utilized, in which the Cu active site is accompanied by auxiliary components. The auxiliary component assists the reaction by locally increasing the concentration of available *H, thus facilitating the hydrogenation step of *OC–CO by improved water dissociation and by locally increasing the concentration of *CO through CO formation.^[10] Water dissociation was shown to be promoted by doping Cu with Ce(OH)_x^[11] or MnO₂.^[11] Examples for CO producing auxiliary components are Ag,^[12–14] Au,^[15] or Zn.^[16]

In 2020, Sargent *et al.*^[4] found by means of machine learning that Cu–Al alloys are interesting candidates with promising binding energies of *H and CO*, and high Faradaic efficiency (FE) for ethylene (> 80%). Later, Kwon *et al.*^[17] reported a FE for ethylene of about 52% using Al₂CuO₄ nanosheets decorated with CuO nanoparticles. They attributed the change of

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selectivity to a stronger adsorption of *CO intermediates for C–C coupling. He *et al.*^[18] performed CO₂RR on a nanosized CuAl₂O₄/CuO catalyst reaching a FE of about 70% for C₂₊-products, postulating an increased coverage of *H favoring hydrogenation of the *HCCOH intermediate. Zhang *et al.*^[19] presented an Al-doped Cu catalyst with a FE for C₂₊-products of 84.5%, proposing regulation of the adsorption energy of oxygen-associated active species on Cu by the introduction of an oxophilic metal. Cheng *et al.*^[20] investigated an oxide-derived CuAl catalyst with a FE of 82% for C₂₊-products, explaining the catalyst performance with a stabilization of Cu(I) by amorphous Al₂O₃. Additionally, tandem electrolyzers were suggested, in which the CO-producing catalyst and the Cu active site are spatially decoupled from each other in two different electrolyzers. In these systems, the CO₂RR is split into two steps at locally and electrochemically separated catalysts. The catalyst system in the first reactor produces CO with high selectivity. The CO-enriched CO₂ feed is then fed to the Cu catalyst-based second reactor, profiting from the favorable kinetics of the CO reduction reaction (CORR) compared to the CO₂RR.^[10,21,22]

We developed and optimized a new catalyst system for the CO₂RR consisting of surface Al-rich Cu/CuO_x composite particles. We optimized the Al content to achieve a high FE for C₂₊-products at high current density. The optimized catalyst was then embedded and investigated in a double flow reactor/tandem electrolyzer setup, in which the first reactor enriches the CO₂ stream with CO using a Ni–Cu-based catalyst, leading to a significant increase in the ethanol production rate of the overall system.

Results and Discussion

The surface Al-rich Cu/CuO_x composites were synthesized using a co-precipitation method by mixing Cu(II) nitrate and Al(III) nitrate in water in the presence of urea. The catalyst precursor was obtained after subsequent calcination at 300 °C in a O₂/N₂-atmosphere. Based on the nominal molar ratio of the precursors for Al of 0.5, 1, 2, and 5% during synthesis, the catalysts in this work are named Cu–Al 0.5 to 5%. Since the synthesis method did not allow for incorporation of higher Al contents (above 5%) the catalyst investigation was limited to Cu–Al 5%. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed a multi-faceted hierarchal structure with distinct differences between the particles (Figure 1a–d). Cu–Al 0.5% exhibits an open structure covered with long thin sheets, Cu–Al 1% has a closed and dense shape with little facets, while Cu–Al 2% and 5% have a rougher structure with outwards pointing dendrites. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was conducted to determine the bulk composition of the catalysts (Figure S4a, b). The bulk atomic ratio of Al and Cu follows the nominal molar ratio of the precursors used in the synthesis with Al atomic ratios of 0.7, 1.3, 2.7, and 5.1% for the 0.5, 1, 2, and 5% nominal ratios, respectively.

To investigate possible segregation phenomena and gain further insights into the chemical states, the near-surface composition was analyzed using X-ray photoelectron spectro-

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of Cu–Al 0.5% (a), Cu–Al 1% (b), Cu–Al 2% (c), Cu–Al 5% (d) after synthesis.

scopy (XPS) and compared to the corresponding nominal composition. For all electrocatalysts, the near-surface region exhibits a significantly higher Al content between 75% and 77% compared to the nominal composition, which is between 0.5 and 5%. (Figure S4c,d, SI). The difference between the bulk and the near-surface composition is associated with the preferential segregation behavior of the Al ions to the surface. This behavior has been previously reported by Wang *et al.*^[23] for Cu–Al alloy thin films with an Al content below 5 at.%. During segregation, Al diffuses through the Cu grain boundaries, forming an aluminum oxide film at the surface, which provides the necessary driving force for the segregation. Moreover, the process is found to be self-limiting, and the film builds up to a thickness of about 3 nm of Al₂O₃ when the temperature during the calcination is below the crystallization temperature of Al₂O₃ (<500 °C).^[23] This explains the similar Al atomic ratio in the near-surface region of our catalysts regardless of the corresponding nominal Al ratios. We additionally performed EDX measurements to investigate the segregation behavior. However, the intensity of the Al signal was too low considering the typical error of EDX ($\pm 1\%$ at.). After characterization, the as-prepared electrocatalysts were tested for electrochemical CO₂ reduction by means of constant-current electrolysis in 1 M KOH. The measurements were performed using a custom-made three-compartment flow cell electrolyzer (Figure S1–S3). Catalyst inks were prepared by mixing the respective catalyst with PTFE particles and subsequently dispersing in isopropanol. After dispersing with a tip-sonicator, the inks were drop-casted with the aid of mild suction on the microporous layer of carbon-paper-based gas diffusion electrodes to achieve a mass loading of 1.3 mg cm⁻².

On-line gas chromatography (GC) and post-electrolysis high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) were used to determine and quantify the gaseous and liquid products at each applied current density. Chronopotentiometry was con-

ducted at each current density for 893 s followed by 7 s of galvanostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (GEIS). The product distribution of Cu–Al 0.5% and 5% (Figure 2a, d) exhibit a similar trend. At low current density (-100 mA cm^{-2}) C_1 -products such as formate and CO have the highest FE, and they are suppressed at higher current density (-400 mA cm^{-2}) due to the corresponding higher applied potentials and driving force (Figure S7–S8, SI) in favor of C_2 -products such as ethylene and ethanol. At low overpotentials, the surface coverage of CO^* is limited, making the formation of C_1 -products the predominant reaction pathway. As the current density increases, the applied potential also rises, and it is well understood that the selectivity is governed by the potential rather than the current. Consequently, the surface coverage of CO^* increases, thereby enhancing the probability of C–C coupling events.^[24] The product distribution of Cu–Al 1% and 2% (Figure 2b,c) exhibits very low selectivity for C_1 -products at low current density, and high selectivity for C_2 -products, compared to Cu–Al 0.5% and 5% at high current density. For Cu–Al 1%, the selectivity towards ethylene and ethanol was increasing at a higher current density up to -300 mA cm^{-2} , which was interrupted at -400 mA cm^{-2} due to electrode flooding.

For Cu–Al 2%, the electrode flooding started already at -200 mA cm^{-2} , causing a rise in H_2 evolution and a decrease in the FE for CO_2RR products. The measured applied potentials during the galvanostatic measurements (Figure S7) give a

possible explanation for the difference in selectivity for the different catalysts. Cu–Al 0.5% and Cu–Al 5% displayed the lowest overpotential for CO_2RR with -0.45 and -0.50 V vs RHE at -100 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. The measurement series for Cu–Al 1% and 2% started at higher overpotentials of -0.57 and -0.6 V vs. RHE , respectively, which are higher than the measured overpotentials at -400 mA cm^{-2} for Cu–Al 0.5% and 5%. Consequently, the measurement series of Cu–Al 1% and 2% started with a higher driving force, which makes C–C coupling and the production of C_{2+} -products more likely. The surface composition of Cu and Al in the as-prepared electrocatalysts was further verified by XPS. High-resolution Cu $2p_{3/2}$ and Al $2p$ spectra are depicted in Figures S5 and S6, respectively. For fitting, we utilized reference data for copper species from ref.^[25] which prioritizes the physical relevance and interpretability of the results over optimizing the quality of the fit. The fitting of the Cu $2p_{3/2}$ region (Figure S5, SI) reveals the presence of different Cu species for the different catalysts, comprising Cu(0) in metallic Cu, Cu(I) in Cu_2O , and Cu(II) in CuO and Cu(OH)_2 . The quantification of Cu species (Figure S4d, SI) shows the predominance of Cu(OH)_2 in all catalysts ($>70\%$). Interestingly, Cu–Al 0.5% and 5% have the highest atomic ratio of Cu(I) species with 17.5 and 12.4%, respectively, while Cu–Al 5% shows the highest atomic ratio of Cu^0 in the series with 17%. In correlation with the CO_2RR measurement, Cu–Al 5% shows the most promising activity for CO_2RR displaying the

Figure 2. Current density-dependent Faradaic efficiencies of the single reactor measurements using Cu–Al 0.5% (a), Cu–Al 1% (b), Cu–Al 2% (c), Cu–Al 5% (d) on a carbon-based hydrophobic gas-diffusion layer. CO_2 flow: 20 ml min^{-1} ; 1 M KOH

highest FE for C_{2+} -products (65%) at -400 mA cm^{-2} , with the second lowest overpotential of -0.59 V vs RHE@ 400 mA cm^{-2} , which can be associated with the most favorable amount of Cu(0) and Cu(I) surface species. For the Al 2p region (Figure S6, SI), one has to consider that Al oxides and hydroxides (Al_2O_3 , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, and AlOOH) are difficult to differentiate by XPS. Nevertheless, the Al 2p region of Cu–Al 5% clearly shows a stronger peak intensity at lower binding energies ($\approx 74 \text{ eV}$) compared to the Al 2p region of the other catalysts (Figure S6, SI), which can be associated with the presence of Al_2O_3 .^[26] This can also explain the favorable catalytic behavior of Cu–Al 5% compared to the other catalysts.

Additional characterization of the spent catalyst after CO_2RR was not performed due to challenges in obtaining the required samples from the complex gas-diffusion electrode. In the next step, Cu–Al 5% was selected for measurements at higher current densities (Figure 3).

The derived selectivities follow the expected trend with a high selectivity for C_1 -products such as CO and formate at low current densities and low cathodic potentials (-25 mA cm^{-2} ; -0.3 V vs RHE) with 42% and 13%, respectively. CO and formate formation are suppressed at high current densities and high cathodic potentials (-800 mA cm^{-2} , -0.63 V vs. RHE) in favor of the formation of C_{2+} -products such as ethylene (48%), ethanol (21%), and propanol (4%). Overall, Cu–Al 5% produces

Figure 3. Product distribution of the single reactor measurements of Cu–Al 5% at higher current density. CO_2 flow: 20 ml min^{-1} ; 1 M KOH.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of (a) the double electrolyzer measurement setup with the feed gas and product gas stream. (b) Current densities sequentially applied to reactor 1, 2, or both reactors.

C_{2+} -products with a FE of 73% at -800 mA cm^{-2} , exhibiting comparable or higher performance to state-of-the-art Cu–Al catalysts (Table S1). To further enhance the selectivity towards C_{2+} -products Cu–Al 1% and 5% were embedded in a double-flow reactor configuration (Figure 4a, S10–S14, SI). This configuration consists of one electrolyzer (reactor 1) for the formation of CO with high selectivity during the CO_2RR , thus enriching the CO_2 stream with CO.

The CO-enriched CO_2 stream from the backside of the gas-diffusion electrode of reactor 1 is then channeled into the second electrolyzer (reactor 2), comprising a gas-diffusion electrode modified with the Cu–Al catalyst. In reactor 1, a Ni–Cu dual-atom catalyst on a 3D microporous carbon substrate was used as a gas-diffusion electrode, which was synthesized via a controllable 2-step pyrolysis method involving the use of a SiO_2 template as porogen. For synthesis and characterization of this catalyst, see ref.^[27]

In reactor 2, gas diffusion electrodes were either modified with Cu–Al 1% or 5%. The measurement sequence (Figure 4b) started by determining the FE and product formation rates of the products formed at the Cu–Al catalyst in reactor 2 at -300 mA cm^{-2} , while reactor 1 was switched off. In the next step, reactor 2 was polarized to a minimal current density of $-1 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ to avoid uncontrolled anodic potentials, which may compromise the integrity of the Cu–Al catalyst.

Reactor 1 was switched to a current density of -400 mA cm^{-2} , and the FE and production rates for mainly CO and H_2 generated at the Ni–Cu catalyst were determined. In the final step, both reactors work simultaneously, and the combined FE and production rates of all products formed in reactor 1 at -400 mA cm^{-2} and reactor 2 at -300 mA cm^{-2} were determined. Based on the single reactor measurements with Cu–Al and Ni–Cu (Figure S9, SI), the selectivity and production rates of the respective products in each individual reactor can be measured and are assumed to remain constant during the entire measurement sequence. Since C_{2+} -products and formate are only produced in reactor 2, any change in selectivity of these products during the combined double-reactor measurement is due to the increased CO concentration in the CO/CO_2 gas feed to reactor 2.

In the case of using Cu–Al 1% (Figure 5a) in the double-reactor measurement, the production rates of formate and ethylene range between $1.5\text{--}1.9 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and $6.4\text{--}6.7 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$, respectively. In contrast, the production rate of ethanol increases from 4.3 to $5.8 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ by 26%, while the production rate of 1-propanol decreases from 0.5 to $0.38 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ by 24%. The combined CO production rate from both single reactors (Figure S11, SI) amounts to $130.8 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$, which is 8.2% higher than the CO production rate in the double-reactor measurement ($120.1 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$). This indicates the preferential conversion of CO formed in reactor 1 to C_{2+} -products. In the double-reactor measurement using Cu–Al 5% in reactor 2 (Figure 5b), the production rates of formate ($6.6\text{--}7.4 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$) and ethylene ($5.6\text{--}6.3 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$) remain constant and comparable to those obtained with Cu–Al 1% as catalyst in reactor 2. In this case, the production rate of ethanol increases by 28%

Figure 5. Comparison of the production rates for formate, ethylene, ethanol, propanol obtained with reactor 2 alone at -300 mA cm^{-2} and when reactors 1 (-400 mA cm^{-2}) and 2 (-300 mA cm^{-2}) are working together using (a) CuAl 1%, and (b) CuAl 5%. Comparison of the production rates for formate, ethylene, ethanol, and propanol obtained with reactor 2 and when reactors 1 and 2 are working simultaneously for CuAl 5% in reactor 2, however, (c) at a lower current density of reactor 1 (-150 mA cm^{-2}). (d) Production rates for H_2 , CO, formate, ethylene, ethanol, and propanol obtained during a long-term measurement using CuAl 5% in reactor 2. Until 7.5 minutes, reactor 2 works alone, after that, reactors 1 and 2 work together. Reactor 1 operates at -200 mA cm^{-2} and reactor 2 at -100 mA cm^{-2} .

from 2.95 to $4.1 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. The production rate of 1-propanol remains constant, ranging between 0.5 and $0.7 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. The combined CO production rate from both single reactors amounts to $132 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and is 10.3% higher than the CO production rate in the double reactor measurement ($118.4 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$). The current density of reactor 1 was lowered to -150 mA cm^{-2} to investigate the influence of a lower CO concentration in the gas feed on the selectivity of Cu–Al 5% in reactor 2 (Figure 5c). The decrease in current density decreases the production rate of CO in reactor 1 by 63.1% from 121.3 to $44.8 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. The corresponding CO concentration in the gas feed channeled into reactor 2 was 3.2% (Table S2). The production rate of formate and 1-propanol remained constant as in the previous measurement at a range between 5.4 – $6.0 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and 0.5 – $0.7 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$, respectively. In contrast, the production rate of ethylene decreased by 15.6% from 6.4 to $5.4 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. The production rate of ethanol increased by 35.2% from 3.17 to $4.89 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. Overall, at lower CO concentrations in the gas feed, the selectivity of the CO_2RR is shifted towards ethanol production at the expense of ethylene. The selectivity of Cu–Al 5% using pure CO in the gas feed would not contribute to the proposed concept in which we aim on the in-situ conversion of CO_2 to CO to convert as

much as possible CO_2 while avoiding the use of hazardous undiluted CO.

Finally, the stability of the double reactor system was investigated by performing a long-term measurement (Figure 5d). In this measurement, reactor 1 and reactor 2 were operated at current densities of -200 and -100 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. The production rate of ethanol was, on average, increased by 4.8% over a period of 5 h.

Conclusions

In summary, we have synthesized and optimized a new Al-surface-rich Cu/Cu oxide catalyst for the CO_2RR with high selectivity towards C_2+ -products, such as ethylene and ethanol, at high current densities. The catalyst shows comparable or higher performance than other state-of-the-art Cu–Al catalysts. Additionally, we investigated the two promising Cu–Al catalysts in a combined dual-electrolyzer setup, in which CO_2 was reduced in the first reactor exclusively to CO using a Ni–Cu dual-atom catalyst. The mixed CO/CO_2 flow was then directed to the Al-surface-rich Cu/Cu oxide catalyst-modified gas-diffusion electrode in reactor 2. The production rate of ethanol was significantly increased using a CO/CO_2 mixed gas feed,

while the production rate of ethylene remained essentially constant.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: CO₂ reduction · Electrocatalysis · Tandem reactor · Selectivity · Catalyst synthesis

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